

Incorporating Social VR Technology in Graduate Students' Collaborative Work: A Comparative User Experience Study of "Horizon Workroom"

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ABSTRACT

This poster reports the objectives and design of a research study that explore the user experience of graduate students collaborating on a hypothetical class assignment in a virtual environment through VR technologies (i.e., Meta Quest headset, "Horizon Workrooms"). Furthermore, participants will perform comparable tasks in two other modalities, Zoom and in-person, to draw comparisons of their collaboration experiences. The results will imply VR technologies' feasibility, strengths, and weaknesses in collaborative work for information-intensive tasks. Data from the pilot session in February suggested that students were enthusiastic about learning and using VR technologies and were highly engaged during the session. And participants thought that it was just as if not easier to perform certain tasks in VR, such as sharing screens and co-browsing web pages. Nevertheless, participants identified several usability problems, such as the difficulty with typing when the keyboard is properly paired, the lags in system response, the inefficiency of using hand tracking for sophisticated tasks, etc., And all three pilot session participants felt tired and varying degrees of motion-sickness after wearing the headset for longer than 30 minutes. Formal testing sessions in April 2023 will reveal more findings regarding the role of VR technologies in academic collaborative work.

KEYWORDS

Virtual reality technology; Collaborative work; User experience design; Usability testing; Immersive learning

INTRODUCTION

Many schools and universities switched to remote instructions with online video conferencing during the COVID-19 pandemic. Some choose to keep the virtual or hybrid mode for its benefits, such as being less geographically limiting and helping to reduce social stress and commute time (Le et al., 2020). Nevertheless, one criticism of the online mode is its lack of interactivity and lower level of in-class engagement. This is where virtual reality (VR) technologies come in, expected to enhance the sense of presence and facilitate social interactions, as the growing research on VR applications in educational settings agrees (Yoshimura & Borst, 2021; Liu & Steed, 2021). Randianti et al. (2019) discovered that VR technology could increase self-and co-presence and elevate motivation and engagement. Some studies focused on incorporating social VR in lecture-style classes to support discussion, presentation, and other activities to enhance teaching and learning interactions (Park & Kim, 2021). Several studies compared participants' collaborations in social VR to the in-person and online video conferencing modes and discovered a higher social presence for VR headsets (HMD for head-mounted devices) (Steinicke et al., 2020) and a preference for a mix of VR headsets and desktop interaction for viewing lectures (Ryu & Kim, 2021).

Despite the evidence for higher engagement levels of people in VR environments, its effect on collaborative task outcomes and performances remains to be seen. Existing literature has shown both benefits and trade-offs that digital and in-person communication tools bring to facilitate collaborative outcomes (Siemens, 2010). Digital affordances, such as fax, voice mails, emails, skype, Voice Over Internet Protocol (VOIP), and online conferencing software, were frequently adopted, especially those distributed teams that connect virtually (M. Anandarajan & A. Anandarajan, 2010). However, studies also suggested that these digital tools have yet to fully overcome the challenges associated with remote collaboration (Cummings & Kiesler, 2005; Deepwell & King, 2009; Siemens, 2010). For instance, dispersed team members may find it challenging to coordinate tasks due to varied time zones (Siemens, 2010). Online conferencing, such as Zoom, incorporates the face-to-face component (e.g., video chat), which is considered essential for collaborative working relationships. However, the two-dimensional nature significantly limits people's sense of presence and immersion during communication, and one can quickly get distracted or disengaged.

Among the growing research on applying VR technologies to facilitate effective collaboration, few have explored VR collaboration for information-intensive tasks (e.g., business meetings in corporate settings; group projects in academic settings). VR enthusiasts embrace the promise of "an immersive connected virtual space" where users could "live" digitally, while conservatives welcome improved real-life outcomes from more productive and efficient collaboration in the virtual environment (Perez, 2022). Regardless, there lacks concrete evidence that the current VR

technologies are feasible alternatives to the in-person work mode. The study attempts to fill the gap by exploring participants' experience working together using Meta Quest 2 headset in Horizon Workrooms.

Objectives and Research Questions

The objectives of this proposed research are two-fold: 1). to test the usability of VR technologies (i.e., Meta Quest 2 and Horizon Workroom) in collaborative teamwork; 2). to compare participants' collaboration experience in three modalities (i.e., in-person, Zoom, VR); for an improved understanding of the potential of VR technologies in collaborative work. The following are the proposed research questions:

RQ1. Explore the usability of using VR technologies to collaborate on group work.

RQ1.1 What usability issues did the participants experience?

RQ1.2 How did the usability of the VR technologies influence participants' task performance?

RQ1.3 What are the participants' sense of immersion and presence during collaboration in the VR environment?

RQ2. How do participants' task performance and experience compare among the three modalities?

RQ3. How do participants feel about VR-enabled work in a collaborative virtual environment?

METHODOLOGY

The study involves ten groups of three participants collaborating in teams during testing sessions featuring three modalities (i.e., VR, Zoom, in-person). In other words, each group will participate in a VR testing session wearing Meta Quest 2 headset and collaborate in a "Horizon Workrooms" meeting room, in an online testing session through Zoom, and in an in-person testing session. On the testing day, before the VR sessions, participants will have a brief training session on how to use the VR headset and the basic features of the Workroom platform. During the testing sessions, participants are expected to follow the testing protocol and utilize the technologies to complete the tasks (see example scenarios). The scenarios and tasks of the three modalities are similar in nature but different in topics. A moderator will join each session to troubleshoot technical issues, record the session, observe, and take notes.

All three testing sessions are videotaped for the generation of valuable data from participants' interactions, conversations, and movements for later analysis of user behaviors, especially those serving as non-verbal cues (e.g., gestures, posture, gaze, sense of presence). Upon completion of all three sessions, participants will complete a post-session questionnaire and engage in a focus group session to discuss and provide feedback through a comparison of the different experiences, focusing on the strengths and weaknesses, productivity, and challenges of different modalities.

PILOT SESSION DISCUSSION

In Mid-November 2022, the research team conducted a test session in a User Experience & Usability class. Ten people, two researchers, one class instructor, and seven students, joined a Horizon Workrooms meeting room with the Meta headsets. The researchers gave a presentation on "VR technologies and UX studies," followed by an exploration of the virtual space and a group discussion for sharing experiences. Students, all novice users of VR technologies, were fascinated with the tools and quickly learned how to navigate the virtual space and interact with the features. During the exploration, students customized their names and avatars, modified the meeting room theme, played with the whiteboard feature, changed seats, and engaged in group discussion. Students encountered severe usability issues despite the high engagement levels and positive experiences with VR technologies. Most students felt tired and dizzy after one hour in the virtual environment with the heavy headset. Students were not satisfied with the half-body avatar and the twisting of hands when they tried to shake hands. The research team ran a pilot session in February 2023, where a group of three participants completed three sets of tasks in the three settings. Preliminary data revealed some usability issues, such as the difficulty with typing when the keyboard is properly paired, the lags in system response, the inefficiency of using hand tracking for sophisticated tasks, etc., Participants suggested that certain tasks, such as sharing screen and co-browsing were easier in a VR environment but it was less efficient for others like collaborating on google slides and group discussion. Participants all felt varying degrees of motion sickness in the VR environment, making it hard to concentrate on tasks. Despite the initial learning curve, participants suggested that the VR technology tested in the study was not difficult to use. One commented, "it felt like a slight improvement over zoom meetings due to an in-person feeling." However, participants did not feel the technology significantly enhanced productivity or efficiency; as another commented, "for what VR is as of right now, it feels more work trying to learn the technology for the sake of using it in work."

CONCLUSION

There is a consensus from the literature and the pilot session that VR technologies are feasible and promising approaches to productive and effective collaborative work, though many feature issues and usability problems need to be discovered and resolved for enhanced user experience. The formal testing sessions will take place in April 2023. Results will likely reveal usability issues with the VR technologies tested in the study and imply aspects of the VR mode that could augment the social experience to yield more productivity and effectiveness in collaborative work.

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APPENDIX

Example VR scenario: Imaging you are collaborating with two fellow classmates virtually for a class project. The project asks you to 1). find a local academic library through online searches; 2). conduct some research on the library website, and gather information about the reference services, research support services, and data services (e.g., availability, forms of delivery, contacts, related resources, etc.) the library provides; 3).prepare a brief presentation of 3-4 slides; and 4). rehearse the presentation.

Example Zoom scenario: Imaging you are collaborating with two fellow classmates virtually for a class project. The project asks you to 1). find a local museum by searching online, 2). do some research on the museum website, and gather information about permanent collections, latest exhibitions, and other community programming (title, description, location, ticket info.), 3).prepare a brief presentation of 3-4 slides, and 4). rehearse the presentation.